

Exploiting Multi-Core Parallelism in Blockchain Validation and Construction

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Abstract

Blockchain validators can reduce block processing time by exploiting multi-core CPUs, but deterministic execution must preserve a given total order while respecting transaction conflicts and per-block runtime limits. This paper systematically examines how validators can exploit multi-core parallelism during both block construction and execution without violating blockchain semantics. We formalize two validator-side optimization problems: (i) executing an already ordered block on p cores to minimize makespan while ensuring equivalence to sequential execution; and (ii) selecting and scheduling a subset of mempool transactions under a runtime limit B to maximize validator reward. For both, we develop exact Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulations that capture conflict, order, and capacity constraints, and propose fast deterministic heuristics that scale to realistic workloads.

Using Ethereum mainnet traces and including a Solana-inspired declared-access baseline (Sol) for ordered-block scheduling and a simple reward-greedy baseline (RG) for block construction, we empirically quantify the trade-offs between optimality and runtime. MILPs quickly become intractable as heterogeneity or core count increases, whereas our heuristics run in milliseconds and achieve near-optimal quality. For ordered-block execution, heuristic makespans are typically within a few percent of the MILP solutions (and can even surpass the MILP incumbent when the solver times out), yielding up to 1.5 speedup with $p = 2$ and 2.3 speedup with $p = 8$ over sequential execution, despite tight ordering constraints. For block construction, the heuristic achieves 99–100% of the MILP optimum reward on homogeneous workloads, and 74–100% of an LP-relaxation upper bound on heterogeneous workloads, where exact optimization often times out. The resulting block-construction throughput scales close to linearly with p , reaching up to 7.9 speedup with $p = 8$ in our experiments. These results demonstrate that lightweight, conflict-aware scheduling and selection can unlock substantial parallelism in blockchain validation, bridging the gap between sequential execution and the true potential of multi-core hardware.

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Keywords and phrases Block construction, Block execution, Deterministic parallelism, Conflict-aware scheduling

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Blockchains process a continuous stream of user transactions that modify a shared replicated state. In most deployed designs (e.g., Ethereum-style execution), validators¹ validate and execute blocks sequentially following a *fixed total order*. While this simplifies reasoning about state, it underutilizes modern multi-core CPUs. In practice, many transactions affect disjoint sets of accounts or storage slots and can be safely executed in parallel without altering the final state. Sequential execution, therefore, limits throughput and increases time-to-finality (i.e., the delay from block proposal to having its transactions finalized on-chain). However, parallelizing block execution is not trivial, since the blockchain state is shared. Reordering or executing concurrently two transactions that conflict² when accessing the state may change the final state. Any viable solution must therefore preserve deterministic, order-equivalent semantics while exploiting conflict-free concurrency.

There is also an economic dimension when validators build blocks. They select transactions from a *mempool* of pending transactions with heterogeneous runtimes and rewards. Since blocks are limited in size by execution time (e.g., with a *gas budget* or *runtime limit*), the question for validators is not “how fast can we execute a given block?” but “how do we select the transactions in a block to maximize the reward?”

In this paper, we study how a validator can leverage multi-core hardware without violating blockchain semantics or economic constraints. We study two complementary validator-side optimization problems, one with a fixed block order and one with flexible selection:

Ordered-Block Scheduling (OBS). Given a block with a fixed transaction set and total order, how should a validator exploit its cores to minimize total execution time while guaranteeing equivalence to sequential execution? This is a **scheduling** problem: transactions that access disjoint sets of accounts or storage slots can run together, while conflicting transactions must respect the block order. We capture conflicts through a **dependency DAG** and aim for a parallel schedule that minimizes the time to execute the whole block (*makespan*), leveraging the inherent parallelism present in existing blocks. This is a classical scheduling problem known as Precedence-Constrained Scheduling, known to be NP-hard on 3 cores and on 2 cores when transactions have execution times in $\{1,2\}$ [14].

Parallel-Block Construction (PBC). On the other hand, when assembling a new block under a runtime limit, the validator has to choose from a mempool of pending heterogeneous transactions that differ in both reward and execution time. Here, the problem is deciding which transactions should be included, and how should they be assigned to cores, so that (i) conflicts are respected, (ii) the overall schedule fits within the runtime limit, and (iii) the total validator reward is maximized. Unlike with OBS, we can now trade off which transactions to include against how efficiently they can be scheduled in parallel. This couples selection and scheduling, reflecting the real economic and system constraints that a validator faces in practice. To our knowledge, prior work has not studied this specific combination of conflict constraints, runtime limit, and validator reward maximization. Observe that PBC is NP-hard, since it generalizes classical NP-hard problems such as knapsack with conflict graphs, and parallel-machine scheduling with conflicts.

¹ Nodes responsible for proposing or verifying blocks, and executing transactions.

² Both write, or one writes and the other reads, the same account or storage slot.

1.2 Contributions

(1) **Problem definitions:** We formalize two validator-side optimization problems:

(i) Ordered-Block Scheduling (OBS), scheduling an ordered block on p cores minimizing makespan, and (ii) Parallel-Block Construction (PBC), selecting and scheduling a subset of mempool transactions on p cores under a runtime limit B to maximize validator reward, all while respecting read/write conflicts.

(2) **MILP formulations:** We present exact **Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulations**³ that capture conflicts and precedence, core capacity, and budget constraints. These MILPs provide optimal baselines on small-to-medium instances, but become intractable at scale; we therefore use them primarily for benchmarking and insight.

(3) **Fast heuristics:** We design **deterministic heuristics** that produce feasible schedules rapidly, trading optimality for orders-of-magnitude higher speed. E.g., the heuristic for OBS is guaranteed to find a schedule with makespan at most $2 - 1/p$ times the optimal.

(4) **Empirical study:** We quantify empirically the limits of parallelism in block execution and construction. Using Ethereum mainnet traces, we compare MILPs and heuristics on both the time taken to find a solution and its quality. We include in the comparison a Solana-inspired declared-access baseline (Sol) for OBS and a simple reward-greedy baseline (RG) for PCB, instantiated using the access sets extracted from Ethereum traces.

We observe that using multiple cores can significantly reduce makespan and increase the block reward relative to sequential block execution. For instance, for OBS we observe that with only 2 cores we can reduce the makespan by a factor of 1.57, and with 8 cores by more than 2. For PBC, the throughput can be increased almost linearly with the number of cores, and the reward increased by a factor of more than 2 even with 4 cores. We also observe that the runtime for solving the MILPs grows steeply with transaction heterogeneity, core count, and runtime limit. However, our heuristics achieve makespans and rewards close to MILP optima when available (and remain competitive against LP-relaxation upper bounds when exact optimization times out), while running in milliseconds.

1.3 Structure of the Rest of the Paper

The article is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews existing literature related to this work. Section 3 presents in detail our model and problems statements. Section 4 discusses the heuristics for OBS. Section 5 presents the MILP formalization of PBC and discusses the heuristics for this problem. Section 6 describes the experiment details. Finally, Section 7, presents and discusses the experimental results, while Section 8 concludes the paper.

2 Related Work

Parallel execution of transactional workloads under determinism and conflict constraints naturally gives rise to classical combinatorial optimization problems in multiprocessor scheduling and packing. In this work, blockchain execution serves as a motivating application domain in which such constraints arise explicitly and at scale. Similar constraints for replica determinism have long been studied in dependable and replicated systems, where concurrent workloads must produce identical outcomes across replicas to ensure state consistency [21].

At its core, OBS is a precedence-constrained makespan scheduling problem on identical processors ($P|prec|C_{max}$). Multiprocessor scheduling with precedence and resource constraints

³ Some formulations use only integer or Boolean variables. We refer to all of them as MILP for simplicity.

129 is NP-hard in general [34, 13], which explains why exact optimization becomes intractable for
 130 realistic block sizes and motivates heuristic or approximate approaches. A standard scalable
 131 approach is list scheduling, with $(2 - 1/p)$ approximation ratio [16, 17]. Although this bound
 132 applies without additional resource conflicts, it motivates greedy event-driven schedulers as
 133 practical baselines when optimal solutions are infeasible. More broadly, the $P|prec|C_{max}$
 134 literature shows that the structure of the precedence partial order can significantly affect
 135 complexity and approximability [29, 28]. Our precedence DAGs arise from intersecting a
 136 total order with a symmetric conflict relation and do not align with known polynomial-time
 137 special cases, inheriting the general NP-hardness. Our goal is thus to understand how simple,
 138 fast heuristics behave on realistic conflict structures and workload heterogeneity.

139 A defining constraint in blockchain execution is fixed-order determinism: correctness
 140 requires equivalence to a specific total order, not merely serializability to some order. Similar
 141 constraints arise in parallel state machine replication and deterministic transactional systems,
 142 where concurrency must respect an externally imposed total order [22, 31, 33]. This motivates
 143 modeling concurrency as a precedence-constrained scheduling problem rather than allowing
 144 arbitrary reordering.

145 Several blockchain systems exploit parallelism to accelerate execution of an already ordered
 146 block. Speculative frameworks such as Block-STM [15], used in Diem [11] and Aptos [2, 3],
 147 execute transactions optimistically in parallel and resolve conflicts via deterministic abort-
 148 and-retry against a preset transaction sequence. Related approaches such as BTM [1]
 149 use read/write-set hints to reduce aborts when access sets are known in advance. Other
 150 designs rely on explicit conflict declarations: Solana requires transactions to declare their
 151 access list, enabling the runtime (Sealevel [32]) to schedule non-overlapping transactions in
 152 parallel while serializing conflicts [35]. Object-centric execution follows a similar philosophy,
 153 representing state as objects and tracking object-level conflicts; Sui Lutriss, in particular,
 154 exploits object-level access metadata to enable parallelism while resorting to consensus
 155 only when shared-object conflicts require total ordering [7]. Across these designs (including
 156 recent systems such as Monad [24]) parallelism is exploited opportunistically, but remains
 157 constrained by the prefix of the total order: a conflicting early transaction can stall later
 158 independent ones rather than being bypassed. OBS makes this restriction explicit by allowing
 159 any order-equivalent execution schedule, thereby formalizing the gap between opportunistic
 160 in-order parallelism and optimal makespan-minimizing execution under limited cores.

161 A substantial body of work studies scheduling under conflict graphs. For unit-time jobs,
 162 conflict-graph scheduling reduces to graph coloring, while heterogeneous execution times
 163 break this equivalence [18]. Empirical studies highlight sensitivity to contention and workload
 164 structure [30], and measurements on Ethereum show conflict graphs dominated by hotspots,
 165 limiting achievable speedups [1, 19, 6]. Complementary semantic analyses characterize when
 166 reordering is safe under read/write effects, abstracting away from optimization objectives
 167 such as makespan or resource-aware selection [4, 5]. Closely related classical models consider
 168 identical-machine scheduling with incompatibility graphs $P|G|C_{max}$, which is NP-hard in
 169 general [8, 23, 9], with exact and MILP-based methods applicable only at moderate scales [25].

170 PBC builds on these models by jointly selecting and scheduling transactions under a hard
 171 runtime budget. It generalizes multiple knapsack [10], knapsack with conflict graphs [27],
 172 and parallel-machine scheduling with rejection [12, 20]. Unlike existing block construction
 173 pipelines, which are typically driven by greedy fee-based selection (e.g., gas price or fee
 174 per gas) and largely ignore parallelizability and interaction effects among transactions [26],
 175 our formulation explicitly captures the interaction between transaction selection, conflicts,
 176 heterogeneous execution times, and core-level makespan. To our knowledge, deployed block

177 assembly pipelines do not incorporate parallelizability directly into transaction selection in a
 178 systematic way, making block construction the primary systems gap our work targets.

179 **3 System Model and Problems Definitions**

180 **3.1 Blockchains**

181 We model a blockchain as a distributed ledger that maintains a shared state and processes a
 182 continuous stream of client-submitted transactions. Pending transactions reside in a *mempool*
 183 until they are selected for inclusion in a block. Each block is proposed by a designated
 184 *validator* (or leader) that assembles transactions from the mempool, subject to an upper
 185 bound on block execution time.

186 **3.2 Transactions**

187 We use the transaction model of Ethereum. Each transaction τ has execution and fee
 188 parameters that govern how it is processed by the validator. When executed, τ consumes a
 189 certain amount of gas $\tau.gasU$. It also has a *Priority Fee*, denoted $\tau.tip$, so that $\tau.reward =$
 190 $\tau.gasU \cdot \tau.tip$ is the reward to the validator that includes τ in a block.

191 We consider two execution-time regimes:

- 192 ■ **Homogeneous** transactions with identical execution time (equivalently identical $\tau.gasU$).
- 193 ■ **Heterogeneous** transactions with varying execution times (equivalently varying $\tau.gasU$).

194 In Ethereum-like settings, simple transfers are often homogeneous, whereas smart contract
 195 transactions are typically heterogeneous. We assume that when a transaction τ is issued, the
 196 client includes an *access list* specifying the set of state keys (accounts and storage slots) $\tau.R$
 197 and $\tau.W$ that τ reads and writes, respectively. In practice, transfers typically access only a
 198 few keys (e.g., sender and receiver of cryptocurrency), whereas smart contract transactions
 199 may access many keys.

200 **Conflicts.** We say that two transactions τ_i and τ_j conflict if and only if they access a
 201 common state key and at least one of them writes to it. I.e., read–read overlaps are not
 202 conflicts, but any overlap involving a write is. Formally,

$$203 \quad \text{conflict}(\tau_i, \tau_j) \equiv \left((\tau_i.W \cap \tau_j.W) \cup (\tau_i.W \cap \tau_j.R) \cup (\tau_i.R \cap \tau_j.W) \right) \neq \emptyset. \quad (1)$$

204 **3.3 Problems Definitions**

205 Our goal is to exploit multi-core hardware to validate and execute transactions efficiently
 206 while preserving blockchain semantics. We assume a validator has an execution environment
 207 that can process up to p transactions in parallel, where p is the number of CPU cores of the
 208 validator. We also assume that the time to execute a transaction τ is proportional to its gas
 209 consumption, which we model as exactly $\tau.gasU$. Then, we can define:

210 ► **Definition 1 (Schedule).** *A schedule S of a set of transactions T on p cores assigns to each*
 211 *transaction in T a core and a starting time to run. Given a schedule S of a set of transactions*
 212 *T on p cores, its makespan, denoted $S.mspan$, is the time to complete the execution (without*
 213 *preemption) of all transactions in T as defined by the schedule S .*

214 We now formalize the two problems.

$$\min \sum_{r \in [R]} y_r \quad (\text{Minimize the number of rounds used}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{r \in [R]} x_{ir} = 1 \quad \forall i \in [n] \quad (\text{Schedule each transaction once}) \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i \in [n]} x_{ir} \leq p \cdot y_r \quad \forall r \in [R] \quad (\text{At most } p \text{ transactions per } r \text{ used}) \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{t=1}^r x_{jt} - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} x_{it} \leq 0 \quad \forall (i, j) \in E, \forall r \in [R] \quad (j \text{ cannot be scheduled before } i) \quad (5)$$

$$y_r \geq y_{r+1} \quad \forall r \in [1..R-1] \quad (\text{Consecutive round usage}) \quad (6)$$

$$x_{ir}, y_r \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in [n], \forall r \in [R] \quad (\text{Binary assignment}) \quad (7)$$

MILP 1: Ordered-Block Scheduling - Homogeneous Transactions

► **Problem 1. Ordered-Block Scheduling (OBS):** Given a block with the sequence of transactions $T = (\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)$, find a schedule S of the transactions in T on p cores, that minimizes makespan $S.mspan$, subject to the constraint that conflicting transactions are not executed in parallel, and they are executed in the order of the sequence.

215

► **Problem 2. Parallel-Block Construction (PBC):** Given a runtime limit B and a set of transactions in the mempool $Mpool = \{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n\}$, select a subset of transactions $T \subseteq Mpool$ and a schedule S of T on p cores such that: conflicting transactions are not executed in parallel, $S.mspan \leq B$, and the total reward $T.reward = \sum_{\tau \in T} \tau.reward$ is maximized.

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4 Ordered-Block Scheduling (OBS)

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In this section we propose algorithms to solve the Ordered-Block Scheduling (OBS) problem. All solutions start by creating a dependency graph. Given a block containing an ordered sequence of transactions $T = (\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)$, we construct a **directed dependency graph** $G = (T, E)$, where each node represents a transaction and each directed edge $(i, j) \in E$ indicates that transaction τ_i must precede τ_j . An edge exists if (i) the two transactions conflict (as defined in Equation (1)), and (ii) $i < j$, ensuring consistency with the block's total order. This graph captures all read/write dependencies that restrict concurrent execution.

4.1 OBS MILP Formulations

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4.1.1 Homogeneous Transactions

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We first consider the homogeneous case in which all the transactions have identical execution time. Since each transaction takes the same amount of time $\tau.t$, we discretize time into rounds R of uniform length. MILP 1 defines the corresponding MILP formulation. Here, R denotes the maximum number of rounds, which must be an upper bound of the rounds required and has to be provided.

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min	M		(Minimize makespan)	(8)
s.t.	$\sum_{c \in [p]} x_{ic} = 1$	$\forall i \in [n]$	(Each trans. in 1 core)	(9)
	$s_i \geq 0$	$\forall i \in [n]$	(Non-negative start)	(10)
	$s_j \geq e_i$	$\forall (i, j) \in E$	(Precedence constr.)	(11)
	$e_i = s_i + t_i$	$\forall i \in [n]$	(End time Definition)	(12)
	$M \geq e_i$	$\forall i \in [n]$	(Makespan is max end)	(13)
	$w_{ijc} \leq x_{ic}$	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}, \forall c \in [p]$		(14)
	$w_{ijc} \leq x_{jc}$	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}, \forall c \in [p]$		(15)
	$w_{ijc} \geq x_{ic} + x_{jc} - 1$	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}, \forall c \in [p]$		(16)
	$z_{ij} = \sum_{c \in [p]} w_{ijc}$	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}$	(Same core flag)	(17)
	$e_i \leq s_j + B((1 - y_{ij}) + (1 - z_{ij}))$,	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}$		(18)
	$e_j \leq s_i + B(y_{ij} + (1 - z_{ij}))$,	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}$		(19)
	$M, s_i, e_i \in \mathbb{N}$	$\forall i \in [n]$	(Continuous variables)	(20)
	$x_{ic} \in \{0, 1\}$	$\forall i \in [n], \forall c \in [p]$	(Binary assignment)	(21)
	$w_{ijc} \in \{0, 1\}$	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}, \forall c \in [p]$		(22)
	$y_{ij}, z_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$	$\forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}$		(23)

MILP 2: Ordered-Block Scheduling - Homogeneous Transactions. Let $\mathcal{P}_{\text{non}} := \{(i, j) : i < j \wedge (i, j) \notin E \wedge (j, i) \notin E\}$ be the set of pairs of transactions without conflicts.

232 **Correctness.** In the solution of MILP 1, $x_{ir} = 1$ iff τ_i is executed in round r ; and y_r
 233 indicates whether the round r is used by any transaction. The objective is to minimize the
 234 number of rounds used, minimizing total execution time (makespan).

235 Constraint (4) enforces the per-round parallelism limit. Since the binary variable x_{ir}
 236 indicates that transaction τ_i executes in round r , the sum $\sum_i x_{ir}$ counts the number of
 237 transactions assigned to that round. At most p cores are available, and hence we require
 238 $\sum_i x_{ir} \leq p \cdot y_r$, where $y_r = 1$ only if round r is actually used. Therefore, no round can host
 239 more than p concurrent transactions, and unused rounds ($y_r = 0$) cannot schedule any work.
 240 Observe that in this case, the solution does not need to assign transactions to specific cores.

241 Constraint (5) enforces precedence. For every directed edge $(i, j) \in E$, transaction τ_i
 242 must complete before τ_j begins. The term $\sum_{t=1}^r x_{jt}$ equals 1 if τ_j is scheduled in a round
 243 $\leq r$, while $\sum_{t=1}^{r-1} x_{it}$ equals 1 if τ_i is scheduled strictly before round r . The inequality

$$244 \quad \sum_{t=1}^r x_{jt} - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} x_{it} \leq 0, \quad \forall r,$$

245 therefore excludes any assignment in which τ_j is placed before τ_i . Together, constraints (4)
 246 and (5) ensure that (i) no more than p transactions execute in parallel in any round and (ii)
 247 all precedence edges are respected in the resulting schedule.

248 4.1.2 Heterogeneous Transactions

249 We now extend the model to the heterogeneous case, in which a block contains both simple
 250 and complex transactions with different execution times. MILP 2 encodes this mixed setting.
 251 The total execution time (makespan) found is denoted by M , and B is a parameter that

252 must be set to be larger than any possible M . The objective is to minimize the makespan
 253 M subject to the assignment, timing, and ordering constraints.

254 Each transaction τ_i is assigned to exactly one core via a binary variable x_{ic} and scheduled
 255 with start and end times s_i and e_i , respectively. Precedence edges $(i, j) \in E$ enforce
 256 dependency order via Equation (11), ensuring that conflicting transactions follow the sequence
 257 order. For non-conflicting pairs, overlap is permitted unless the two transactions are assigned
 258 to the same core. Same-core assignment is captured by the auxiliary variable w_{ijc} (the logical
 259 AND of x_{ic} and x_{jc}), and z_{ij} indicates whether the pair shares any core. If $z_{ij} = 1$, the
 260 binary selector y_{ij} determines their order: $y_{ij} = 1$ means τ_i precedes τ_j ; otherwise, $y_{ij} = 0$
 261 means the reverse. In Equation (18) and Equation (19), observe the following cases:

- 262 ■ $z_{ij} = 0$: the constraints have no effect due to the runtime limit term B .
- 263 ■ $z_{ij} = 1, y_{ij} = 1$: Equation (19) has no effect, only Equation (18) applies, yielding $e_i \leq s_j$.
- 264 ■ $z_{ij} = 1, y_{ij} = 0$: Equation (18) has no effect, only Equation (19) applies, yielding $e_j \leq s_i$.

265 These conditional constraints ensure that same-core transactions are serialized.

266 **Correctness.** Constraint (9) ensures that every transaction is assigned to exactly one
 267 core. Precedence edges $(i, j) \in E$ are enforced by (11), which requires that any dependent
 268 transaction τ_j starts only after τ_i has completed. Together, these constraints preserve the
 269 total order implied by the dependency graph. For non-conflicting pairs, the coupling of w_{ijc} ,
 270 z_{ij} , and y_{ij} ensures that same-core pairs are serialized by (18)–(19), while pairs on different
 271 cores remain unconstrained. Together, these properties ensure that MILP 2 produces a
 272 feasible schedule that respects all dependencies and minimizes the overall makespan M .

273 4.1.3 Complexity

274 Both MILP formulations grow quickly with the number of transactions n and cores p . The
 275 homogeneous case (MILP 1) involves $\mathcal{O}(nR)$ binary variables and $\mathcal{O}(nR + |E|R)$ constraints,
 276 while the heterogeneous case (MILP 2) expands to $\mathcal{O}(n^2p)$ binary variables, $\mathcal{O}(n)$ integer
 277 variables, and $\mathcal{O}(n^2p + |E|)$ constraints. Each formulation generalizes well-known NP-hard
 278 multiprocessor scheduling problems, implying that exact solutions become computationally
 279 prohibitive as n and p increase.

■ **Algorithm 1** BUILD DAG(). Recall the conflict definition from Equation (1)

```

1: function BUILD DAG( $T$ )
2:    $V \leftarrow \{\tau : \tau \in T\}; E \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3:   for each  $i \in [1..n - 1]$  do
4:     for each  $j \in [i + 1..n]$  do
5:       if  $\text{conflict}(\tau_i, \tau_j)$  then  $E \leftarrow E \cup \{(\tau_i, \tau_j)\}$ 
6:       end if
7:     end for
8:   end for
9:   return  $G = (V, E)$ 
10: end function

```

Algorithm 2 SCORINGOBS()

```

1: function SCORINGOBS( $G$ )
2:   for each  $\tau \in V$  do
3:      $succ[\tau] \leftarrow \{\tau' : (\tau, \tau') \in E\}$ 
4:      $pred[\tau] \leftarrow \{\tau' : (\tau', \tau) \in E\}$ 
5:      $outdg[\tau] \leftarrow |succ[\tau]|$ 
6:      $indg[\tau] \leftarrow |pred[\tau]|$ 
7:   end for
8:    $Q \leftarrow \{\tau : outdg[\tau] = 0\}$   $\triangleright$  Set of sinks
9:   while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
10:     $\tau \leftarrow$  any element in  $Q$ 
11:     $Q \leftarrow Q \setminus \{\tau\}$ 
12:     $hgt[\tau] \leftarrow \tau.t + \max_{\tau' \in succ[\tau]} \{hgt[\tau']\}$ 
13:     $vol[\tau] \leftarrow \tau.t + \sum_{\tau' \in succ[\tau]} \{vol[\tau']\}$ 
14:    for each  $\tau' \in pred[\tau]$  do
15:       $outdg[\tau'] \leftarrow outdg[\tau'] - 1$ 
16:      if  $outdg[\tau'] = 0$  then  $Q \leftarrow Q \cup \{\tau'\}$ 
17:    end if
18:  end for
19: end while
20: for each  $\tau \in V$  do
21:    $pri[\tau] \leftarrow (-hgt[\tau], -vol[\tau], -|succ[\tau]|, \tau.id)$ 
22: end for
23: return( $pri, indg, succ$ )
24: end function

```

Algorithm 3 SCHEDULEOBS()

```

1: function SCHEDULEOBS( $T, p, pri, indg, succ$ )
2:    $now \leftarrow 0$ 
3:    $free \leftarrow [1..p]$   $\triangleright$  Free cores
4:    $running \leftarrow \emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Trans. that are running
5:    $ready \leftarrow \{\tau \in T : indg[\tau] = 0\}$   $\triangleright$  Ready tx
6:   repeat
7:     while ( $ready \neq \emptyset$ )  $\wedge$  ( $free \neq \emptyset$ ) do
8:        $\tau \leftarrow \arg \min \{pri[\tau'] : \tau' \in ready\}$ 
9:        $ready \leftarrow ready \setminus \{\tau\}$ 
10:       $running \leftarrow running \cup \{\tau\}$ 
11:       $start[\tau] \leftarrow now$ 
12:       $end[\tau] \leftarrow now + \tau.t$ 
13:       $core[\tau] \leftarrow$  any element in  $free$ 
14:       $free \leftarrow free \setminus \{core[\tau]\}$ 
15:    end while
16:     $now \leftarrow \min \{end[\tau] : \tau \in running\}$ 
17:     $S \leftarrow \{\tau \in running : end[\tau] = now\}$ 
18:     $running \leftarrow running \setminus S$ 
19:    for each  $\tau \in S$  do
20:      for each  $\tau' \in succ[\tau]$  do
21:         $indg[\tau'] \leftarrow indg[\tau'] - 1$ 
22:        if  $indg[\tau'] = 0$  then
23:           $ready \leftarrow ready \cup \{\tau'\}$ 
24:        end if
25:      end for
26:       $free \leftarrow free \cup \{core[\tau]\}$ 
27:    end for
28:  until ( $running = \emptyset$ )  $\wedge$  ( $ready = \emptyset$ )
29:  return ( $start, core$ )
30: end function

```

Algorithm 4 OBS Heuristics

```

1: Input: Block  $T = (\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)$ . Number of cores  $p$ .
2: Output: A schedule with the start time  $start[\tau]$  and core  $core[\tau]$  assigned to each transaction  $\tau \in T$ .
3:  $G \leftarrow \text{BUILDDAG}(T)$ 
4:  $(pri, indg, succ) \leftarrow \text{SCORINGOBS}(G)$ 
5:  $(start, core) \leftarrow \text{SCHEDULEOBS}(T, p, pri, indg, succ)$ 

```

280 **4.2 Heuristics**

281 Our heuristics (Algorithms 1–4, use a conflict-aware greedy scheduler, guided by transaction
282 priorities. It proceeds in three stages:

283 **(1) DAG construction.** For the given block $T = (\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)$, we build a dependency DAG
284 $G = (V, E)$ (Algorithm 1). Each node is a transaction $\tau \in T$, and we add an edge (τ_i, τ_j)
285 whenever τ_i and τ_j conflict (as defined in Equation (1)) and $i < j$. This DAG encodes all
286 precedence constraints that must be respected at execution time.

287 **(2) Priority scoring.** We then extract structural information from G (Algorithm 2). For
288 each transaction τ , we compute:

289 ■ $hgt[\tau]$: the critical-path length rooted at τ (i.e., τ 's own execution time plus the maximum
290 downstream height),

291 ■ $vol[\tau]$: the total execution volume of τ and its descendants,

292 ■ $|succ[\tau]|$: the fan-out of τ .

293 A single backward pass over the DAG computes these values. We assign each transaction a
 294 deterministic priority key $pri[\tau] := (-hgt[\tau], -vol[\tau], -|succ[\tau]|, \tau.id)$, which favors long
 295 critical paths first, then heavier subtrees, then higher fan-out, and $\tau.id$ breaks ties.

296 **(3) Transaction scheduling.** Finally, we simulate the block execution on p cores (Algorithm 3).
 297 The scheduler maintains (i) a set of *ready* transactions (initially those with in-degree zero
 298 in G), (ii) a set of *running* transactions with assigned cores and finish times, and (iii) the
 299 current time *now*. Whenever any core becomes free, we schedule the highest-priority ready
 300 transaction to that core. When a transaction finishes, we decrement the in-degree of its
 301 successors and add any successor with zero in-degree to the set of ready transactions. This
 302 event-driven loop continues until all transactions are scheduled. Algorithm 4 combines these
 303 steps into a complete pipeline.

304 **Complexity.** The DAG construction in Algorithm 1 compares each ordered pair (τ_i, τ_j)
 305 with $i < j$, and is therefore $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ in the worst case.⁴ The preprocessing pass in Algorithm 2
 306 performs a single reverse topological traversal plus constant work per edge, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(n + |E|)$.
 307 The scheduler in Algorithm 3 runs as an event-driven simulation with at most n schedule
 308 events and n completion events; using a priority queue for the ready set, this is $\mathcal{O}(n \log n + |E|)$.
 309 Overall, the heuristic end-to-end runtime is dominated by DAG construction and is $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$
 310 in the worst case. Regarding the approximation ratio, since the heuristic implements a
 311 list scheduling, we know that it gives a schedule with makespan at most $2 - 1/p$ times the
 312 optimal.

313 5 Parallel-Block Construction (PBC)

314 We now turn to the block-construction problem. Given a mempool $Mpool = \{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n\}$
 315 of pending transactions, we construct an undirected conflict graph $G = (Mpool, E)$ whose
 316 nodes correspond to the transactions in $Mpool$, with an edge $(\tau_i, \tau_j) \in E$ if and only if the
 317 two transactions conflict (as defined in Equation (1)). The block runtime limit B and the
 318 conflicts must be respected in the schedule obtained for the transactions selected from T
 319 to be included in the block. This setting combines both *selection* (which transactions to
 320 include) and *scheduling* (how to assign them across cores) under dependency and time budget
 321 constraints.

322 5.1 PCB MILP Formulations

323 5.1.1 Homogeneous Transactions

324 We first consider the homogeneous case, where all transactions have identical execution time t .
 325 The block gas budget B therefore allows at most $R = \lfloor B/t \rfloor$ execution rounds. MILP 3
 326 formalizes the selection-and-scheduling problem for this setting. Here, $x_{ir} = 1$ if and only if
 327 transaction τ_i is selected and executed in round r , yielding a validator reward $w_i := \tau_i.reward$
 328 for its inclusion in the block.

329 The problem can be viewed as a weighted packing task: we fill each of the R rounds with
 330 up to p non-conflicting transactions, choosing the subset that maximizes total weight (i.e.,
 331 reward $\sum_i w_i$) while respecting both conflict and capacity constraints.

⁴ In practice, this can often be pruned with sparse access lists, but we analyze the dense upper bound.

$$\max \sum_{i \in [n]} \sum_{r \in [R]} w_i x_{ir} \quad (\text{Maximize total weight}) \quad (24)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{r \in [R]} x_{ir} \leq 1 \quad \forall i \in [n] \quad (\text{Each trans. scheduled at most once}) \quad (25)$$

$$\sum_{i \in [n]} x_{ir} \leq p \quad \forall r \in [R] \quad (\text{At most } p \text{ transactions per round}) \quad (26)$$

$$x_{ir} + x_{jr} \leq 1 \quad \forall (i, j) \in E, i < j, \forall r \in [R] \quad (\text{No conflicting pair in same round}) \quad (27)$$

$$x_{ir} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in [n], \forall r \in [R] \quad (\text{Binary assignment}) \quad (28)$$

MILP 3: Parallel Block Construction - Homogeneous Transactions

$$\max \sum_{i \in [n]} w_i v_i \quad (\text{Maximize total weight}) \quad (29)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{c \in [p]} x_{ic} = v_i \quad \forall i \in [n] \quad (\text{One core max}) \quad (30)$$

$$e_i - s_i = t_i v_i \quad \forall i : i \in [n], \quad (\text{Time activation}) \quad (31)$$

$$0 \leq s_i \leq Bv_i, 0 \leq e_i \leq Bv_i \quad \forall i : i \in [n], \quad (\text{Activation bounds}) \quad (32)$$

$$e_i - s_j \leq B(1 - y_{ij}), \quad \forall (i, j) : (i, j) \in E \wedge i < j, \quad (\text{Conflicts}) \quad (33)$$

$$e_j - s_i \leq B(y_{ij}), \quad \forall (i, j) : (i, j) \in E \wedge i < j, \quad (\text{Conflicts}) \quad (34)$$

$$w_{ijc} \leq x_{ic}, w_{ijc} \leq x_{jc} \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}, \forall c \in [p] \quad (35)$$

$$w_{ijc} \geq x_{ic} + x_{jc} - 1 \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}}, \forall c \in [p] \quad (36)$$

$$z_{ij} = \sum_{c \in [p]} w_{ijc} \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}} \quad (\text{Same core flag}) \quad (37)$$

$$e_i \leq s_j + B((1 - y_{ij}) + (1 - z_{ij})), \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}} \quad (38)$$

$$e_j \leq s_i + B(y_{ij} + (1 - z_{ij})), \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{non}} \quad (39)$$

$$s_i, e_i \in \mathbb{N} \quad \forall i \in [n] \quad (\text{Integer assignment}) \quad (40)$$

$$v_i, w_{ijc}, x_{ic}, y_{ij}, z_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i, j \in [n], \forall c \in [p] \quad (\text{Binary assignment}) \quad (41)$$

MILP 4: Parallel Block Construction - Heterogeneous Transactions. Let

$\mathcal{P}_{\text{non}} := \{(i, j) : i < j \wedge (i, j) \notin E \wedge (j, i) \notin E\}$ be the set of pairs of transactions without conflicts.

332 **Correctness.** Constraint (25) ensures that each transaction is scheduled at most once
 333 across all rounds. Constraint (26) enforces the validator's core capacity, limiting each round
 334 to at most p concurrent transactions. Constraint (27) excludes conflicting pairs from being
 335 assigned to the same round, preserving deterministic execution semantics. Together, these
 336 constraints guarantee that every feasible solution corresponds to a conflict-free parallel
 337 schedule that fits within the gas budget. The objective (24) then selects the optimal subset
 338 of transactions that maximizes total validator reward under these feasibility constraints.

339 5.1.2 Heterogeneous Transactions

340 We now extend to the case of transactions with heterogeneous execution times t_i . MILP 4
 341 jointly models transaction selection and parallel scheduling under conflicts, core capacity,

Algorithm 5 SCHEDULEPBC()

```

1: function SCHEDULEPBC( $T, p, B, pri, confs$ )
2:    $now \leftarrow 0$ 
3:    $free \leftarrow [1..p]$   $\triangleright$  Free cores
4:    $running \leftarrow \emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Trans. running
5:    $sel \leftarrow \emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Trans. completed
6:    $ready \leftarrow T$   $\triangleright$  Pending transactions
7:    $deferd \leftarrow \emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Conflicting with running
8:   repeat
9:     while ( $ready \setminus deferd \neq \emptyset$ )  $\wedge$  ( $free \neq \emptyset$ )
10:    do
11:       $\tau \leftarrow \arg \min\{pri[\tau'] : \tau' \in ready \setminus deferd\}$ 
12:      if ( $running \cap confs[\tau] \neq \emptyset$ ) then
13:         $deferd \leftarrow deferd \cup \{\tau\}$ 
14:        continue
15:      end if
16:       $ready \leftarrow ready \setminus \{\tau\}$ 
17:      if  $now + \tau.t > B$  then
18:        continue
19:      end if
20:       $running \leftarrow running \cup \{\tau\}$ 
21:       $sel \leftarrow sel \cup \{\tau\}$ 
22:       $start[\tau] \leftarrow now$ 
23:       $end[\tau] \leftarrow now + \tau.t$ 
24:       $core[\tau] \leftarrow$  any element in  $free$ 
25:       $free \leftarrow free \setminus \{core[\tau]\}$ 
26:      end while
27:       $now \leftarrow \min\{end[\tau] : \tau \in running\}$ 
28:       $S \leftarrow \{\tau \in running : end[\tau] = now\}$ 
29:       $running \leftarrow running \setminus S$ 
30:      for each  $\tau \in S$  do
31:         $free \leftarrow free \cup \{core[\tau]\}$ 
32:         $deferd \leftarrow deferd \setminus confs[\tau]$ 
33:      end for
34:      until ( $running = \emptyset$ )  $\wedge$  ( $ready = \emptyset$ )
35:      return ( $sel, start, core$ )
36: end function

```

342 and runtime constraints. The binary variable v_i determines whether transaction τ_i is selected
343 to be included in a block. If selected ($v_i = 1$), it must be assigned to exactly one core via x_{ic}
344 and executed during the time window $[s_i, e_i]$ with duration t_i . Conflict edges $(i, j) \in E$ forbid
345 temporal overlap between the conflicting transactions. Their mutual ordering is decided
346 by y_{ij} , enforced through constraints (33)–(34). For non-conflicting pairs, overlap is allowed
347 unless they share a core. Same-core assignment is captured by w_{ijc} , the logical AND of x_{ic}
348 and x_{jc} , and z_{ij} which flags whether a pair shares any core. If $z_{ij} = 1$, the pair must be
349 serialized, with order selected by y_{ij} as enforced in constraints (38)–(39). The objective (29)
350 maximizes the total weight $\sum_{i \in [n]} w_i v_i$ subject to gas and core limits, balancing which
351 transactions are included and how they are scheduled.

352 **Correctness.** Constraint (30) ensures that every selected transaction occupies exactly
353 one core, while (31) and the activation bounds couple start and end times to the selection
354 variable v_i . Conflict pairs $(i, j) \in E$ are serialized via constraints (33)–(34), preventing
355 overlapping execution regardless of order. For non-conflicting transactions, same-core co-
356 assignment is detected by w_{ijc} and summarized by z_{ij} ; if $z_{ij} = 1$, constraints (38)–(39)
357 enforce a valid ordering determined by y_{ij} . These constraints guarantee that all selected
358 transactions can be executed within the gas limit B without violating conflict or resource
359 dependencies. The objective then identifies the highest-reward feasible subset and schedule.

360 5.1.3 Complexity

361 Both the homogeneous (MILP 3) and heterogeneous (MILP 4) formulations of PCB generalize
362 NP-hard problems such as weighted parallel-machine scheduling and multidimensional
363 knapsack. The homogeneous formulation involves $\mathcal{O}(nR)$ binary variables and $\mathcal{O}(nR + |E|R)$
364 constraints, while the heterogeneous one expands to $\mathcal{O}(n^2p)$ binary variables and $\mathcal{O}(n^2p + |E|)$
365 constraints. Solver time thus grows sharply with block size and heterogeneity, motivating
366 the use of fast approximation methods.

Algorithm 6 SCORINGPBC()

```

1: function SCORINGPBC( $G$ )
2:   for each  $\tau \in V$  do
3:      $confs[\tau] \leftarrow \{\tau' : ((\tau, \tau') \in E) \vee$ 
4:        $((\tau', \tau) \in E)\}$ 
5:      $d[\tau] \leftarrow |confs[\tau]|$ 
6:      $\rho[\tau] \leftarrow \tau.reward / \tau.t$ 
7:      $pri[\tau] \leftarrow (-\rho[\tau], d[\tau], -\tau.reward, \tau.id)$ 
8:   end for
9:   return ( $pri, confs$ )
10: end function

```

Algorithm 7 PBC Heuristics

```

1: Input: Set  $T = \{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n\}$ . Number of cores
   $p$ . Time/Gas limit  $B$ .
2: Output: A schedule with a list of selected
  transactions  $sel$  and its start time  $start[\tau]$  and
  core  $core[\tau]$  assigned to each  $sel$  transaction
   $\tau \in sel$ .
3:  $G \leftarrow \text{BUILDDAG}(T)$ 
4: ( $pri, confs$ )  $\leftarrow$  SCORINGPBC( $G$ )
5: ( $sel, start, core$ )  $\leftarrow$ 
6:   SCHEDULEPBC( $T, p, B, pri, confs$ )

```

5.2 Heuristics

Our mempool heuristics (Algorithms 5–7) greedily assemble a conflict-free parallel schedule of transactions under the runtime limit B . They combine lightweight scoring and event-driven dispatch to approximate the MILP objective efficiently.

Priority Scores: For each transaction τ in the mempool, we compute its value density as $\rho[\tau] := \frac{\tau.reward}{\tau.t}$ and $d[\tau]$ is the number of transactions with which τ conflicts. The composite priority key $pri[\tau] := (-\rho[\tau], d[\tau], -\tau.reward, \tau.id)$, favors high-reward, low-conflict transactions, breaking ties deterministically by $\tau.id$.

Transaction Scheduling: Using the priorities above, we iteratively dispatch transactions to free cores (Algorithm 5). At each step, the scheduler maintains three sets: *ready* transactions (eligible for execution), *running* transactions (currently executing), and a *deferred* set of candidates that conflict with running ones. When a core becomes free, the highest-priority non-conflicting transaction is launched, provided the cumulative runtime used remains within B . On each completion event, the corresponding transaction is removed from *running*, its conflicts are cleared from *deferred*, and its core is released. This process continues until either the runtime budget or transaction pool is exhausted. Algorithm 7 integrates both steps into a full end-to-end pipeline.

Complexity. The conflict graph construction has complexity $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. Computing transaction degrees and priorities has also complexity $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. The event-driven scheduler then performs $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ priority operations plus $\mathcal{O}(np)$ updates for dispatch and completion across p cores. Overall, the heuristic runs in polynomial time, dominated by graph construction and conflict detection.

6 Experiments

As described, we study two validator-side tasks: (i) OBS: scheduling a fixed ordered block on p cores to minimize makespan and (ii) PBC: selecting and scheduling mempool transactions to maximize reward under a runtime budget B . We evaluate our MILP formulations and conflict-aware greedy heuristics on transaction traces extracted from the Ethereum mainnet for blocks 21,631,019 - 21,635,079, spanning 15 - 16 January 2025. Each transaction trace records the execution outcome, including the read and write sets, gas used, and internal call tree produced by the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM). From these traces, we extract per-transaction `gasUsed`, `to/from` addresses, storage keys accessed, and all contract calls. Conflicts are then derived exactly from overlapping read/write sets (as described in Equation (1)). In addition to comparing our heuristics against the MILP baselines, for OBS, we include a baseline inspired by Solana’s declared-access execution model (Sealevel), where transactions expose read/write account sets up front and the runtime schedules only non-conflicting transactions

402 to run concurrently [32, 35]. We denote this baseline by **Sol**. On our Ethereum-derived
 403 instances (using the access sets extracted from traces), we implement Sol as a deterministic,
 404 event-driven scheduler that scans transactions in block order and dispatches each transaction
 405 as soon as a core becomes available and it does not conflict with currently running transactions.
 406 For PBC, we instead compare against a simple **reward-greedy** baseline (**RG**) that uses the
 407 same non-conflicting dispatch rule but selects candidates purely by reward-based priority
 408 (i.e., favoring higher-fee transactions, breaking ties by arrival order), yielding a lightweight
 409 selection-and-scheduling baseline under the conflict constraints.

410 6.1 Hardware and Software

411 All experiments were run on a Dell PowerEdge R7615 equipped with a single AMD EPYC
 412 9654P (96 cores/ 192 threads) and ≈ 1.5 TiB RAM, running Ubuntu 24.04.3 LTS. We use
 413 MATLAB R2025b for the heuristics and invoke HiGHS 1.7.1 through MATLAB’s `intlinprog`
 414 for MILPs. We do not limit the number of threads: MATLAB and HiGHS may use all
 415 available cores. Unless otherwise specified, solver tolerances follow MATLAB defaults. We
 416 set a maximum running time of $MaxTime := 6000$ s. for the solver. All heuristics are
 417 deterministic; repeated runs on the same workload yield identical schedules.

418 6.2 Workload Construction

419 Our experiments use real Ethereum transactions to synthesize controlled workloads for
 420 both problems. To control workload size across configurations $(R$ or $B, p, X)$, we build
 421 synthetic workloads by taking consecutive mainnet transactions in their original order and
 422 re-aggregating them, rather than relying on variable on-chain block boundaries.

423 **Trace filtering.** We parse transactions and separate them into two categories:

- 424 ■ **Homogeneous** transactions: pure ETH transfers that do not invoke any smart contract,
 425 and therefore use the default gas amount of 21,000 units.
- 426 ■ **Heterogeneous** transactions: the full set of observed transactions, including contract
 427 calls with varying performed computations.

428 Each transaction’s gas used $\tau.gasU$ is taken directly from its execution trace, and its execution
 429 time $\tau.t$ is normalized proportionally to gas use.

430 **OBS workloads.** For each experiment, we collect a sequence of transactions (Homogeneous
 431 or Heterogeneous) in their original blockchain order, ignoring actual block boundaries. We
 432 then aggregate this sequence into blocks of size determined by either (a) the number of
 433 rounds R for homogeneous cases, each round able to process up to p transactions; or (b) the
 434 gas budget B for heterogeneous cases, stopping once $\sum_{\tau} \tau.gasU \approx B$. For each configuration
 435 $(R$ or $B, p)$, we construct five consecutive, non-overlapping workloads. This corresponds to
 436 simple transactions extracted from 219 blocks (9,600 transactions) of mainnet data for the
 437 homogeneous case, and 14 blocks (2,460 transactions) of mainnet data for the heterogeneous.

438 **PBC workloads.** To emulate a validator’s mempool, we use a sliding window of transactions.
 439 Given configuration (R, p, X) or (B, p, X) , where X is the *pool factor*, we select a candidate
 440 pool containing approximately X times the transactions (or total gas) that fit in one block:

- 441 ■ Homogeneous case: $R \cdot p \cdot X$ transactions;
- 442 ■ Heterogeneous case: $B \cdot p \cdot X$, where $\sum_{\tau} \tau.gasU \approx B$.

443 The corresponding MILP and heuristic then select and schedule a feasible subset for inclusion.
 444 For each configuration, we again construct five independent workloads. In practice, this
 445 corresponds to simple transactions extracted from 2,989 blocks (137,200 transactions) of

446 mainnet data for the homogeneous case, and 24 blocks (4, 280 transactions) of mainnet data
 447 for the heterogeneous case.

448 **Experiment parameters.** For homogeneous transactions, experiment duration is discretized
 449 into equal-length rounds, so progress is naturally parameterized by the number of rounds R ,
 450 with per-round capacity p . For heterogeneous transactions, we parameterize the experiment
 451 duration by a continuous runtime limit B , which directly captures feasibility under varying
 452 processing times. For homogeneous cases, we evaluate each configuration with rounds
 453 $R \in \{10, 30, 100\}$, cores $p \in \{2, 4, 8\}$, and (when applicable) pool factor X . For mempool
 454 experiments we use $X \in \{2, 4, 8\}$ in the homogeneous case and $X \in \{2, 4\}$ in the heterogeneous
 455 case. For heterogeneous cases, we set the runtime limit to $B \in \{210K, 630K, 2100K\}$. For
 456 every R or B, p, X configuration, we run five non-overlapping workloads and report the mean.

457 6.3 Hypotheses

458 We evaluate the following hypotheses:

459 **H1 (MILP scaling):** MILP runtime grows steeply with problem size and heterogeneity.

460 **H2 (Heuristic speed):** The conflict-aware greedy heuristics runs orders of magnitude faster
 461 than MILPs across all settings.

462 **H3 (Heuristic quality):** The heuristics yield parallel schedules that approach the performance
 463 of MILP solutions.

464 **H4 (Practical speedup):** The heuristics yield parallel schedules with significant speedup
 465 with respect to sequential executions.

466 7 Results and Discussion

467 We now present results for OBS and PBC under homogeneous and heterogeneous workloads.
 468 Unless stated otherwise, each reported value is the mean over five independent instances per
 469 configuration. We compare our conflict-aware greedy heuristic (GH) to the MILP baselines
 470 and to the additional baselines introduced in Section 6.

471 7.1 Ordered-Block Scheduling

472 We first compare the runtime of the MILP solver against GH and Sol for OBS on homogeneous
 473 workloads with $p \in \{2, 4, 8\}$ and $R \in \{10, 30, 100\}$. Solver time increases rapidly with both
 474 R and p , growing from milliseconds on small instances to thousands of seconds for $R=100$,
 475 $p=8$, confirming the expected combinatorial scaling (**H1**). GH and Sol, by contrast, remain
 476 consistently below 0.1s even at the largest configuration (**H2**). Table 1 shows that on
 477 homogeneous instances, GH matches the MILP solution across all tested (R, p) (**H3**). Sol is
 478 close but degrades on larger instances; for example, at $R=100$, Sol requires 106.2 rounds for
 479 $p=2$ and 118.4 rounds for $p=4$, compared with 100 rounds for MILP/GH. This indicates that
 480 simple in-order dispatch leaves avoidable stalls even when conflicts are known. GH achieves
 481 a speedup similar to that of MILP, which is near-linear for these low-conflict homogeneous
 482 transfer workloads. This gap reflects the difference between a reactive in-order dispatcher
 483 (Sol), which may block on transient conflicts, and our proactive scheduling approach (GH),
 484 which pre-computes a conflict-respecting schedule that smooths execution by prioritizing
 485 transactions on the critical path.

486 We observe a similar runtime separation on heterogeneous workloads, parameterized
 487 by gas budget $B \in \{210K, 630K, 2100K\}$. As B grows, solver runtime escalates by orders
 488 of magnitude with both p and B (**H1**), exceeding our 6,000s execution time limit for the

	R = 10		R = 30		R = 100	
p	MILP/GH	Sol	MILP/GH	Sol	MILP/GH	Sol
2	10/2	10.2/1.96	30/2	30.2/1.99	100/2	106.2/1.88
4	11/3.64	13.2/3.03	30.6/3.92	38/3.16	100/4	118.4/3.38
8	11.6/6.9	15.2/5.26	31.6/7.6	44.6/5.38	100/8	115.2/6.94

■ **Table 1** OBS - Homogeneous transactions: Average number of rounds and average speedup (related to the sequential runtime) for MILP solver and greedy heuristic (identical results) compared to Solana (Sol).

	B = 210K		B = 630K		B = 2100K	
p	GH	Sol	GH	Sol	GH	Sol
2	100.49/1.65	103.69/1.59	100.29/1.57	107.56/1.45	98.68 [†] /1.81	117.15 [†] /1.51
4	100/1.82	102.9/1.77	100/1.98	105/1.86	100/2.15	111.03/1.94
8	100/2.26	101.19/2.22	100/2.03	101.13/2	77.67 [†] /2.29	81.77 [†] /2.17

■ **Table 2** OBS - Heterogeneous transactions: Heuristics solution makespan M as a percentage of the optimal solution found by the MILP solver. For the values marked with [†] (columns $B=2100K$), the MILP hit the 6000s timeout limit: for $p=2, 3$ of 5 workloads timed out; for $p=8$, all 5 did; the reported MILP incumbents are feasible but not guaranteed optimal. The second part of a cell shows the corresponding speedup achieved related to the sequential runtime.

B = 210K				
	X = 2		X = 4	
p	MILP	GH	MILP	GH
2	99.81/1.61	99.60/1.84	100/1.9	96.84/1.86
4	99.34/3.27	95.47/3.25	91.89/3.87	88.71/3.88
8	100/4.26	98.83/3.82	66.61/4.33	92.21/7.35

B = 630K				
	X = 2		X = 4	
p	MILP	GH	MILP	GH
2	95.24/1.98	94.84/1.99	54.83/1.94	74.74/1.99
4	77.9/3.39	91.9/3.89	14.67/1.98	75.42/3.96
8	15.27/1.41	81.24/7.44	2.94/1	74.03/7.9

■ **Table 3** PBC - Heterogeneous transactions: MILP incumbent and GH rewards - $\sum_{\tau} \tau \cdot \text{reward}$ of the block generated as a percentage of the LP-relaxation upper bound on achievable reward reported by the solver.

489 largest configuration. GH and Sol, by contrast, remain sub-second throughout (**H2**). Table 2
 490 confirms that GH’s makespans differ from the MILP’s best integer solutions by at most a
 491 few percent (and in some cases even improve upon the solver’s incumbent when the solver
 492 exceeds our runtime limit) and also consistently outperforms Sol (**H3**). Overall speedups
 493 over 1-core sequential execution are in the $\sim 1.6\text{--}2.3\times$ range (Table 2), confirming **H4** but
 494 also highlighting a key limitation of OBS: even with many cores, a fixed consensus order and
 495 conflict-induced dependencies cap achievable parallelism.

496 7.2 Parallel-Block Construction

497 For PBC on homogeneous workloads, we compare runtimes while varying the pool factor
 498 $X \in \{2, 4, 8\}$ and cores $p \in \{2, 4, 8\}$. MILP time again increases steeply with X and p , while
 499 GH and RG remain in the millisecond range (**H1, H2**). For homogeneous mempool instances,
 500 GH and RG achieve reward values that are consistently close to the MILP optimum across
 501 all tested configurations ($X \in \{2, 4, 8\}$, $p \in \{2, 4, 8\}$, and $R \in \{10, 30, 100\}$). This shows
 502 that when execution times are uniform, greedy conflict-aware packing is sufficient to recover
 503 near-optimal block reward, supporting **H3**. Moreover, RG’s performance closely matches

504 GH across the entire configuration grid, indicating that the simple reward-greedy baseline
 505 remains competitive on homogeneous workloads. Also, in this homogeneous setting both
 506 GH and RG achieve essentially perfect parallel utilization, yielding a speedup equal to the
 507 number of cores (i.e., exactly p) across the tested configurations, supporting **H4**.

508 For heterogeneous workloads, where both execution times and rewards vary, exact MILP
 509 optimization becomes prohibitive. We therefore normalize both solver and heuristic rewards
 510 by the MILP’s LP-relaxation upper bound⁵. Table 3 presents these normalized values for pool
 511 factors $X \in \{2, 4\}$, runtime limits $B \in \{210K, 630K\}$, and cores $p \in \{2, 4, 8\}$. GH schedules
 512 achieve between 74–100% of the relaxation bound, while MILP incumbents frequently remain
 513 well below 20% of the LP bound at large B or p , having reached the time limit before closing
 514 the optimality gap (**H1,H2**). Even in the most challenging settings, GH constructs high-
 515 reward, feasible blocks within milliseconds, thereby confirming its scalability and practical
 516 robustness (**H3**). We also evaluated the reward-greedy baseline (RG) on the same instances
 517 and observed near-identical results to GH in this setting; for clarity, we therefore omit RG
 518 from the table. The speedup values obtained are close to the value of p , especially for large
 519 B (**H4**), which means that using parallelism in this problem achieves almost linear speedup.
 520 Comparing with Table 2, we observe a big improvement when transaction selection is possible
 521 versus only scheduling a pre-determined block.

522 We conducted additional conflict-stress experiments with artificially high contention and
 523 found that GH is consistently at least as fast as RG and yields higher total reward while
 524 scheduling the same number of transactions, with an average improvement of 7.7% over RG.
 525 In fact, a simple scenario in which GH will drastically improve over RG is one in which all
 526 transactions have execution time and reward 1, and the first B transactions in the mempool
 527 conflict with each other, while all the other transactions (at least $p \cdot B$) conflict with the
 528 first B but not with themselves. (This scenario may arise if the first B transactions write in
 529 the same item x , while the rest reads x .) Then, RG will schedule the first B transaction in
 530 sequence, not able to schedule other transactions in parallel. On the other hand, GH will
 531 schedule $p \cdot B$ transactions, always executing p transactions in parallel.

532 **8** Conclusions

533 In this paper, we presented a systematic exploration of validator-side parallelism in blockchain
 534 transaction execution. We formulated two complementary optimization problems: (i)
 535 executing an already ordered block on multiple cores while minimizing makespan, and
 536 (ii) selecting and scheduling a subset of mempool transactions under a gas budget to
 537 maximize validator reward. For both, we developed exact MILP formulations to serve as
 538 optimal baselines, and efficient deterministic heuristics that scale to realistic workloads.
 539 We also include a Sealevel-inspired declared-access baseline (Sol) to represent a practical,
 540 conflict-avoiding in-order execution strategy.

541 Our evaluation on Ethereum mainnet traces demonstrate that MILP runtimes grow steeply
 542 with problem size, heterogeneity, and core count, confirming the computational hardness of
 543 the problems. Our heuristics remain sub-second across all settings, produce solutions that are
 544 close to those of the MILP, and reduce makespan and increase reward by a sensible amount
 545 with respect to sequential scheduling. Across our experiments, GH consistently matches or
 546 improves upon Sol in solution quality, with particularly clear advantages as conflict intensity
 547 increases, while maintaining comparable (sub-second) scheduling overhead.

⁵ The MILP solver used initially reports the LP-relaxation bound, obtained by relaxing integrality.

548 From a systems perspective, our findings show that even simple, conflict-aware scheduling
 549 strategies can make effective use of available cores, narrowing the gap between theoretical and
 550 practical parallelism in blockchain execution. In particular, the mempool-based formulation
 551 provides a path toward constructing blocks that are inherently “parallel-friendly,” coupling
 552 selection and scheduling to improve both performance and economic efficiency.

553 **Limitations and Future Work.** Our evaluation uses the `gasUsed` field from Ethereum
 554 traces as a proxy for execution time. This provides a consistent and realistic measure for the
 555 ordered-block problem, but it is only an approximation of the actual runtime. In practice,
 556 execution time and gas usage may diverge due to hardware, client, or EVM implementation
 557 differences. Moreover, in the mempool formulation, reordering transactions could change
 558 their effective gas consumption in the case of conflicts. A second limitation is that our current
 559 heuristics largely resolve conflicts through local, greedy decisions based on static conflict
 560 information. A promising direction is to design more holistic conflict-aware policies that
 561 reason globally about contention (e.g., hotspots, conflict clusters, or anticipated serialization)
 562 when selecting and scheduling transactions.

563 Exploring how to model such non-determinism in execution time while maintaining the
 564 safety guarantees provided by conservative gas limits is left for future work. Similarly, an
 565 open systems question is how best to maintain and update dependency graphs efficiently as
 566 new transactions arrive and blocks are mined. This also suggests online heuristics that update
 567 priorities as conflicts evolve, rather than relying on a fixed, one-shot ordering. Designing low-
 568 overhead data structures or incremental graph-maintenance schemes for this purpose will be
 569 essential for bringing these scheduling techniques into production blockchain environments.

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